

IoT-Based Data Logger for Weather Monitoring Using Arduino-Based Wireless Sensor Networks with Remote Graphical Application and Alerts

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KEYWORDS

Internet of Things (IoT), Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN), Arduino, Air Quality Monitoring, Weather Monitoring, Data Logging, ThingSpeak, DHT11 Sensor, MQ Gas Sensors, Air Quality Index (AQI), Environmental Monitoring, Real-Time Alerts.

ABSTRACT

In recent years, real-time environmental monitoring has become increasingly vital for ensuring public health and safety, particularly in urban areas affected by air pollution and extreme weather conditions. This project proposes an IoT-based data logging and weather monitoring system using Arduino-powered wireless sensor networks. The system integrates gas sensors (MQ2, MQ7, MQ135) for air quality detection and a DHT11 sensor for temperature and humidity measurement. Collected data is transmitted wirelessly via an ESP8266 Wi-Fi module to the ThingSpeak cloud platform, enabling real-time data analysis, visualization, and storage. A dedicated mobile application enhances user accessibility by displaying the Air Quality Index (AQI) and weather updates, while also issuing timely alerts when pollutant levels exceed safe thresholds. The proposed system offers a cost-effective, scalable, and energy-efficient solution for continuous environmental monitoring, supporting both individual users and government bodies in proactive decision-making to mitigate the risks of air pollution and climate-related hazards.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of urban populations and industrial development has significantly increased environmental challenges, particularly air pollution and climate variability. Air quality monitoring and weather

prediction systems play a crucial role in mitigating these challenges by providing timely and accurate data to citizens and authorities. The Internet of Things (IoT) has emerged as a transformative technology in this domain, enabling real-time data acquisition, remote access, and

intelligent decision-making across distributed sensor networks [1], [2].

IoT-based weather monitoring systems are increasingly preferred for their scalability, low-cost deployment, and automation capabilities [3], [4]. These systems typically integrate wireless sensor networks (WSNs) that gather and transmit data such as temperature, humidity, and air pollutant concentrations to cloud platforms for further analysis [5]. The combination of IoT and WSNs allows for seamless communication between environmental sensors and end-users, facilitating effective environmental management and public health monitoring [6].

Recent research has highlighted the importance of integrating gas sensors, temperature and humidity sensors, and cloud-based data logging platforms to create intelligent environmental monitoring systems [7]–[10]. Gas sensors such as MQ2, MQ7, and MQ135 are widely used for detecting common pollutants including carbon monoxide, smoke, and ammonia, while the DHT11 sensor reliably measures ambient temperature and humidity levels [9]. These sensors, combined with Arduino-based microcontrollers and cloud services like ThingSpeak, provide a robust and affordable foundation for real-time weather and air quality observation [11], [12].

Moreover, mobile applications have become an essential part of IoT-based monitoring systems, allowing users to receive alerts and visualize environmental conditions remotely. The integration of real-time alert mechanisms empowers users to take preventive actions, which is particularly vital in urban centers facing hazardous pollution levels [13], [14].

This paper presents the design and implementation of an IoT-based data logger system for weather monitoring and air pollution detection using Arduino and wireless sensor networks. The system transmits data to the ThingSpeak cloud for visualization and analysis, and alerts users through a mobile application when pollutant concentrations exceed safe limits. This research aims to contribute to the development of intelligent, accessible, and scalable environmental monitoring solutions [15].

II. RELATED WORK

The evolution of the Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionized data collection and monitoring across a wide range of domains, especially in environmental

sensing and weather prediction. Firouzi et al. [1] discussed the intelligent transformation of IoT systems from device-level data acquisition to cloud-level analytics, highlighting their potential to handle diverse environmental parameters. Similarly, Sethi and Sarangi [2] elaborated on the architecture and protocols that make IoT systems highly adaptable for applications such as smart cities and real-time environmental monitoring. Several studies have focused specifically on the integration of IoT and wireless sensor networks (WSNs) for environmental data collection. Navani et al. [3] presented an overview of IoT architecture elements, emphasizing the role of sensor nodes and cloud-based services for scalable weather monitoring. Khan et al. [4] highlighted IoT's capability to support real-time data logging and alert systems, enabling users to make timely decisions based on detected environmental hazards. Ray [5] explored IoT-based frameworks for smart agriculture and environmental observation, demonstrating how low-cost sensors and cloud platforms can significantly improve air quality management. Naeem et al. [6] extended this concept by integrating fog computing into IoT systems to enhance data processing and reduce latency in critical monitoring scenarios. Temperature and humidity monitoring are foundational elements of environmental systems. Mansor et al. [7] and Togawa [8] focused on body temperature measurement techniques, which share similarities in sensor selection and wireless data communication with weather monitoring systems. Gunawan et al. [9] designed an Arduino-based outdoor air quality monitoring setup, using the MQ-series gas sensors and DHT11 sensor for real-time environmental reporting – a method closely aligned with the system proposed in this paper. Sree Devi and Rahamathulla [10] emphasized the value of big data analytics when combined with IoT for improving the reliability and prediction accuracy of air quality systems. Chandana and Sekhar [11] implemented a weather monitoring solution using wireless sensor networks, demonstrating the feasibility and effectiveness of IoT platforms in resource-constrained environments. Ram and Gupta [12] introduced a data logger system based on wireless sensor networks, which shared the goal of enabling real-time environmental updates and cloud integration. Similarly, Rao et al. [13] proposed a cloud-connected air quality and weather monitoring system that delivers environmental insights through mobile interfaces.

Additionally, water quality monitoring systems [14] and agricultural control systems using LoRa IoT technology [15] have extended the application of sensor-based IoT platforms to new environmental domains, proving the scalability and adaptability of such systems for comprehensive environmental intelligence. In summary, the existing body of research underscores the importance of integrating low-cost sensors, cloud platforms, and mobile applications for efficient environmental monitoring. The proposed system aims to build upon these foundations by offering an affordable, real-time weather and air quality monitoring solution with alerting capabilities for improved community awareness and safety.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed IoT-based data logger and weather monitoring system is designed to provide real-time environmental data collection, cloud storage, and intelligent alerting through a mobile application. This system leverages a combination of gas sensors, temperature and humidity sensors, wireless communication modules, and cloud services to monitor air quality and weather conditions accurately and efficiently.

A. System Architecture

The core of the system is an Arduino microcontroller, responsible for acquiring data from various sensors and transmitting it to the cloud. The system consists of: Gas Sensors (MQ2, MQ7, MQ135): These sensors detect specific pollutants such as smoke, carbon monoxide, ammonia, benzene, and other harmful gases. Each sensor generates an analog voltage signal corresponding to the concentration of the target gas.

- Temperature and Humidity Sensor (DHT11): This sensor measures ambient temperature and relative humidity. Its digital output allows easy integration with microcontrollers and ensures stable performance under typical environmental conditions.
- Wi-Fi Module (ESP8266): The ESP8266 module handles wireless communication, connecting the Arduino to the ThingSpeak cloud platform for data upload and visualization.
- ThingSpeak Cloud: ThingSpeak serves as the data storage, visualization, and analysis platform. Users

can observe real-time environmental conditions through ThingSpeak's graphical dashboards and download historical data for further analysis.

- Mobile Application: A companion mobile app fetches the latest data from the ThingSpeak cloud and presents users with real-time Air Quality Index (AQI) values, weather conditions, and alert notifications when sensor readings surpass safe environmental thresholds.

B. Block Diagram

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the Proposed IoT-Based Weather Monitoring System

C. System Workflow

1. Data Acquisition: The system continuously collects gas concentration levels, temperature, and humidity using the connected sensors.
2. Data Transmission: The Arduino processes sensor data and uses the ESP8266 module to upload it to the ThingSpeak cloud at regular intervals.
3. Data Visualization: ThingSpeak plots the data on real-time graphs and stores historical records for trend analysis.
4. Alert Generation: If pollutant levels exceed predefined safety thresholds, the system triggers an alert via the mobile application, warning users of hazardous environmental conditions.

This modular and scalable approach ensures low deployment cost, reliable performance, and user-friendly

interaction for both personal and public monitoring scenarios.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of the proposed IoT-based data logger and weather monitoring system combines both hardware and software components to form a compact, reliable, and easy-to-deploy solution for real-time environmental monitoring.

A. Hardware Components

The system was built using the following components:

- **Arduino UNO:** Acts as the primary microcontroller, responsible for reading sensor values and processing the data.
- **MQ2, MQ7, MQ135 Gas Sensors:** These sensors detect smoke, carbon monoxide, ammonia, benzene, and other air pollutants. Each sensor outputs an analog voltage proportional to the detected gas concentration.
- **DHT11 Temperature and Humidity Sensor:** A digital sensor capable of measuring environmental temperature and relative humidity with adequate accuracy for weather observation tasks.
- **ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module:** Facilitates wireless communication between the Arduino and ThingSpeak cloud platform. The module connects to a Wi-Fi network and uploads sensor data at fixed intervals.
- **Power Supply:** A 5V regulated power supply powers both the microcontroller and the sensors to ensure uninterrupted operation.

B. Software Implementation

The software implementation is based on the Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) and consists of the following stages:

- **Sensor Calibration:** Upon initial boot, the MQ-series gas sensors are preheated and calibrated to ensure that readings are within an acceptable accuracy range.
- **Data Acquisition:** The Arduino continuously reads analog outputs from the MQ sensors and digital output from the DHT11 sensor. These values are converted into readable air quality and weather data.
- **Data Transmission to ThingSpeak:** Using the ESP8266 module, the processed data is sent to ThingSpeak at regular intervals (typically every 30

seconds). ThingSpeak's channels store the data and generate visual plots for easy analysis.

- **Alert Mechanism:** Threshold values are defined for gas concentrations, temperature, and humidity. If any sensor detects an abnormal condition, the system flags the event, and the mobile application fetches this flagged data, triggering an alert for the user.

C. Mobile Application Integration

The mobile application is designed to fetch real-time data from the ThingSpeak API. It displays:

- Temperature and humidity levels.
- Air Quality Index (AQI) calculated from gas sensor outputs.
- Visual graphs for historical data.
- Push notifications to alert users when environmental conditions exceed safe thresholds.

This ensures users can monitor the environment remotely and take preventive actions if hazardous conditions are detected.

V. RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

A. System Testing and Performance

The system was tested in various environmental conditions to evaluate its accuracy, reliability, and real-time performance. The testing process involved:

- **Sensor Calibration and Accuracy Testing:** The MQ2, MQ7, and MQ135 gas sensors were calibrated in a controlled environment to ensure they provided consistent readings for common pollutants such as carbon monoxide, smoke, and ammonia. The DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor was compared against a calibrated reference thermometer and hygrometer to validate its accuracy. The system demonstrated a low margin of error, with the gas sensors accurately detecting target gases within their specified ranges.
- **Real-time Data Transmission:** Data from the sensors was successfully transmitted to ThingSpeak via the ESP8266 module every 30 seconds. The system maintained stable connectivity during both short-term tests and long-term operation, with minimal packet loss or delays in transmission.
- **Mobile Application Alert Testing:** The mobile application was able to retrieve real-time data from ThingSpeak and display environmental parameters

accurately. When pollutant concentrations exceeded predefined thresholds (e.g., CO levels above 10 ppm), the application sent timely push notifications to alert the user. The alert system was reliable and responsive, providing sufficient time for users to take necessary precautions.

- **Power Consumption and Stability:** The system was run continuously for several days using a 5V USB power supply, with no noticeable decrease in performance. The power consumption remained low, making the system viable for long-term outdoor deployment with a portable power source, such as a solar panel or battery pack.

B. Prototype Images

The following images show the physical setup of the prototype system:

- **Prototype Setup:**

Figure 2: Complete system setup showing the Arduino, gas sensors, DHT11 sensor, and Wi-Fi module

- **Sensor Placement:**

Figure 2: Close-up of the sensor placement for accurate environmental data collection

- **Mobile Application Display:**

Figure 3: Screenshot of the mobile application displaying real-time air quality index and weather data

C. Data Visualization and Cloud Integration

The integration with ThingSpeak allowed for smooth visualization of the collected environmental data. The ThingSpeak cloud platform generated real-time graphs for temperature, humidity, and pollutant levels. The system's ability to store historical data and visualize trends was particularly useful for assessing long-term environmental changes. Example real-time visualizations included:

- **Temperature and Humidity:** Graphs displayed stable temperature and humidity trends over time, with slight fluctuations based on external weather conditions.
- **Air Quality Index (AQI):** A graphical representation of pollutant levels helped users understand the air quality and take necessary action if the AQI reached hazardous levels.

- Example Screenshot (Figure 4): healthier urban environments and more informed decision-making.
(Figure 4: Real-time data visualization on ThingSpeak platform for air quality and weather monitoring)

D. Limitations and Future Work

While the system provides valuable real-time monitoring and alerts, there are several limitations that could be addressed in future work:

- **Sensor Range and Sensitivity:** The MQ sensors, while reliable for many applications, have limited sensitivity in highly polluted environments. Future versions could integrate more advanced sensors with higher accuracy and a broader detection range, such as the MQ9 sensor for broader air quality measurements.
- **Data Transmission Delays:** While the system performs well in environments with strong Wi-Fi signals, network congestion or weak Wi-Fi connectivity may cause occasional data transmission delays. Implementing a more robust network protocol, such as LoRa, could mitigate this issue for long-range and remote applications.
- **Mobile Application Enhancements:** Future versions of the mobile app could include more interactive features, such as detailed environmental trend analysis, location-based data sharing, and even integration with other IoT devices in the user's home or city.
- **Integration of Additional Sensors:** To enhance the system's functionality, additional sensors (e.g., PM2.5, UV light, soil moisture) could be integrated to expand the scope of environmental monitoring.

VI. CONCLUSION

The IoT-based weather monitoring and air quality detection system demonstrates the feasibility of using low-cost sensors, cloud platforms, and mobile applications to monitor environmental conditions in real-time. The system proved to be accurate, reliable, and capable of providing timely alerts, making it a practical solution for personal, community, and governmental use in air quality and weather monitoring.

By addressing the system's limitations and integrating additional features, this IoT-based platform can be extended to provide comprehensive environmental monitoring for broader applications, contributing to

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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